

Federated Network Intelligence Orchestration for scalable and automated FL-based anomaly detection in B5G Networks

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Abstract—Network Intelligence management in Beyond 5G networks embraces the exciting challenge of addressing scalability, dynamicity, interoperability, privacy, and security concerns. These are essential steps towards achieving the realization of truly ubiquitous AI-based analytics, empowering seamless integration across the entire Continuum (Edge, Fog, Core, Cloud). To address these challenges, this paper presents a model-driven Federated learning approach for managing and Orchestrating the Network intelligence needed to detect and prevent cyber-attacks. The system has been integrated into a B5G Security Framework, leveraging the multi-domain and multi-tenant Orchestrator thereby endowing the Network intelligence with key features for automated and scalable deployment of FL-agents and AI-based anomaly detectors, strengthening the reaction capabilities to counter cyber-attacks. The presented FL-based model-driven system allows interoperability and extensibility in the management of the FL system.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, 6G, Orchestration, anomaly detection

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing research interest in the field of Network Intelligence orchestration and Federated Learning (FL) for anomaly detection in B5G/6G networks. The real-time data analytic required by critical applications are moving the AI-based processes to edge devices, which are closer to the data sources. The edge devices run intelligence processes that need to be orchestrated seamlessly across the Continuum (IoT-Edge-Fog-Core-Cloud). In this sense, edge intelligence which refers to bringing training data and low-level learning tasks to the edge of the network can be realized through Federated Learning approach.

Federated Learning was proposed by McMahan *et. al* in [1] as an alternative to centralized machine learning in which a global model can be trained from decentralized data, thus preserving its privacy during the learning process. Over the last few years, it has been used to design intrusion detection frameworks due to its efficiency and scalability, among other aspects. FL brings several benefits to these networks, such as leveraging network control, improving behavior prediction, and achieving accurate anomaly detection, since all these processes require ubiquitous AI spanned across the Continuum.

However, the usage of FL in B5G introduces several challenges, including orchestration and management of the FL federation, scalability, automation, management of non-IID, i.e., non-independent and identically distributed data, interoperability across B5G tenants/domains, and extensibility, among others.

To address these challenges, future architectures will need AI processes to be deployed and coordinated in a distributed way, configured and managed dynamically and on demand. Policy-based security orchestration paradigm can be a powerful ally as it can decide and manage how the security tools (security enablers) should be enforced. Besides, the policy-based approach allows users defining intents/policies that can be transformed into real security deployments/configurations across the infrastructure without requiring knowledge about underlying technologies. The combination of these two approaches enables the creation of an efficient and scalable system on demand for deploying and decommissioning real-time agent-based FL-driven intrusion detection systems across network segments. On the one hand, FL allows the training of a centralized global model from decentralized data, while preserving its privacy and improving efficiency and scalability by bringing the training computation closer to the edge of the network, where the data is stored. FL-based anomaly detection allows converging on global and leveraged AI models, that can be used to detect, predict and alert from anomalies and intrusions, performing timely mitigation actions that minimize the consequences of a potential attack. On the other hand, policy-based orchestration ensures that the infrastructure is interoperable, extensible and well managed across heterogeneous domains, governing Software-Defined Networking (SDN) or Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technologies to provide key network properties such as scalability, reliability and dynamicity to network intelligence management.

In this regard, the main contribution of this paper is the design of a B5G security management framework, enhanced with decentralized anomaly detection capabilities, that is conceived to strengthen security, reliability, and privacy across the Continuum. Namely, the paper proposes a model-driven Network Intelligence Security Orchestration mechanism aimed

to manage and choreograph the Federated Learning processes. An FL-policy model is presented to achieve interoperability and extensibility, while the orchestration system proposed ensures desirable features in terms of scalability, context awareness, dynamicity, and reaction capabilities in order to prevent and counter cyberattacks.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews the existing literature and research related to the Federated Learning approach and network intelligence. Section III introduces the framework and describes the design of orchestration, decision and detection, showing its behavior in different stages. Finally, Section IV provides conclusions and highlights the lines for this work to be continued.

II. RELATED WORK

Generally, signature-based intrusion detection systems have proven to be inefficient in detecting zero-day attacks [2], which are a high-probability threat in next-gen mobile networks. Therefore, machine or deep-learning based intrusion detection systems have better applicability in this type of environments, and combined with training based on Federated Learning could offer an enhanced and optimal solution. Although several approaches have been presented over the last few years in this line [3], some of them adapted even to work over 5G networks [4], none of them leverages Federated Learning for model training.

Federated Learning applied to secure various types of network environments has gained a lot of interest over the last few years due to its privacy and efficiency [5]. More precisely, some recent works, such as [6], explore the application of this methodology to detect anomalies using long- and short-term (LSTM) neural networks fed with real network traffic. Some other works, such as [7], present an exhaustive literature review on how Federated Learning can be applied to the field of communication and networking.

Nevertheless, there are other approaches which try to mitigate some of the main B5G FL challenges, in order to reduce communication latency or energy consumption, while improving the model's accuracy. Some of them present a hierarchical methodology that involves the participation of devices at the edge of the network, such as Mobile Edge computing (MEC) servers [8].

In addition, several works have been also presented in the line of not only Federated Learning orchestration but general Network Intelligence orchestration (NI). In [9], authors present an architectural model to cover the requirements and specifications of NI instances in the next-gen mobile networks. More specifically, in [10], authors propose OrchestRAN, a prototype orchestration framework built upon the Open Radio Access Network (RAN) to address the orchestration challenges of a given network optimization/automation objective. Also, [11] applies AI techniques to build a framework that extends the relevant standard specifications with some building blocks based on this paradigm, to control, manage and orchestrate a 5G network.

However, these existing works, although address some of the key challenges of NI orchestration and management, do not provide solutions to deploy, configure and manage in real-time FL-based network intrusion detection systems achieving the desired lever of interoperability and scalability across the Continuum. Our approach covers this problem by a policy-based network functions orchestration that is capable of deploying, in real-time and based on the infrastructure needs, several FL agents and the corresponding detection engines to ensure a private, efficient, scalable and fully customizable detection framework updated to the current threat status of the network.

III. NETWORK INTELLIGENCE ORCHESTRATION

The incorporation of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning to 5G/B5G networks has caused a quantitative and qualitative leap since these technologies applied to a dynamic orchestration allow intelligent analysis, detection and decision making on-demand, deploying in any network segment in the Continuum plethora of management and control planes, improving security, resource management and services which leads to a better quality of service (QoS), lower latency, greater energy efficiency, among other. This section provides a description of the designed architecture, which leverages the Inspire-5GPlus project reference architecture, extending it with different components such as Monitoring Agents, Federated Learning Agents, Aggregators and AI-based Anomaly Detection Engines. All these modules would be part of the whole management system, capable of monitoring, learning, detecting and alerting about potential attacks in a closed loop. At the same time, the learning process should resist possible attacks such as model poisoning or membership inference attacks, for which differential privacy techniques that add noise to exchanged model updates, as described in [12], can be used, and trust scores can be leveraged in an agent selection process for each federated training to minimize poisoning risks. Moreover, the architecture should make possible the re-training of implied detection models if necessary, i.e., when a threat is detected, and also be extensible, scalable, and reliable.

A. Architecture

Figure 1 shows the proposed distributed architecture, composed of three main planes: (i) E2E Management Domain, which is in charge of governing all the lower-level management domains, (ii) Management Domains, with one Security Management Domain (SMD) per network segment, e.g., Radio-Access Network (RAN), Transport Network and Core Network Domain, and (iii) Infrastructure Resources, where network segments and their physical and virtual functions are present. Each Management Domain is self-governed, can belong to a different provider and can be replicated multiple times thanks to virtualization. In addition, each domain would follow a Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute (MAPE) loop and would be capable of orchestrating the Network Intelligence across its local domain resources, from the UE or final devices to the components located at the core segment of the network.

Fig. 1: High-level vision of network intelligence orchestration for B5G networks

They can deploy a Federated Learning architecture, composed of several Aggregators and multiple Agents connected to them, serving as a decentralized Intrusion Detection System (IDS) that alerts of security threats potentially taking place in the infrastructure in real-time. Although in Figure 1 FL actors are only included in the RAN Management and E2E domains for simplicity, they can also be within the SAE of the other domains, i.e., Transport and Core. This enables the federated training since multiple agents should be involved.

One of the main reasons for adapting and extending the Inspire-5Gplus reference architecture, is that it implements the ZSM approach provided by the ETSI, providing essential capabilities such as automation, self-managing and self-healing. This represents a suitable starting point for building future and next-gen functionalities, so it has been used to show a high-level vision of Network Intelligence orchestration for beyond-5G networks. Following, the different modules that composes each SMD are briefly described:

Security Analytics Engine (SAE). This module analyzes the information/alerts provided by the probes distributed across the infrastructure. The same module at E2E level focus on analyzing and correlating events and security issues from different domains to detect issues that could be affecting different domains. In our proposal, this block will be extended to include FL Aggregation, FL Agent and Anomaly Detection features. Those features, as well as its related models, operations and workflow will be detailed later.

Decision Engine (DE). It provides dynamic decisions about required countermeasures according to the alerts received from the Security Analytics Engine. At E2E level, these decisions also consider multiple domains to provide E2E countermeasures.

Security Orchestration (SO). This module is in charge of orchestrating and enforcing proactive and reactive security poli-

cies. Especially, it decides how the requested security policies will be enforced by selecting the most suitable enforcement point, and managing dynamic deployments if required. At E2E level the behaviour is similar, but orchestration processes consider whole domains instead of low-level infrastructure as enforcement points.

Policy & SSLA Management (PSSLAM). This module provides multiple features to allow policy-based operations. Policy refinement process allows the refining of high-level policies into medium-level policies or SSLAs into the policy models the operator uses. Policy translation allows translating medium-level policies into final infrastructure configurations. A policy repository is in charge of providing traceability as well as security policy templates to facilitate policy building to both, users and automated reactive processes. As the infrastructure is provided at SMD level, policy translations occur at this level, whereas policy refinement can occur in both, E2E and SMD to refine high-level policies provided by users into medium-level policies.

Trust management (TM). This module gathers infrastructure information as well as security events to calculate trust metrics. Trust metrics are retrieved during orchestration processes to be included in the orchestration decisions, and additionally in FL Agent selection processes to mitigate model poisoning attacks. At E2E level, Trust modules also consider the whole underlying domains of trust. This values are also used during E2E orchestration stages to decide the most trustable domain.

Data Services (DS). They access and store inter and intra-domain data, including infrastructure and security information. The rest of the modules rely on them for gathering and storing data when required. For instance, infrastructure probes update information whereas security orchestrators and FL Agents access them for knowing the current status of the infrastructure and retrieve traffic statistics for model training.

Integration fabric. The ZSM methodology utilizes integration fabrics as a means of communication and security between SMDs both within and outside the domain. Additionally, integration fabrics offer service management functions like registration and discovery that are necessary for inter and intra-domain operations. These fabrics enable access to data services while ensuring secure communication within the fabric. Essentially, integration fabrics not only facilitate various communication modes but also provide valuable security and management features within a service mesh. It will allow authenticating FL Agents in the architecture, and exchange across the Continuum, among others, FL-based policies, AI models, monitoring data, system models, management and control data.

Infrastructure resources. They are composed of all the hardware and software components the domain provides to facilitate computing, networking and storage features among others. Located at the enforcement plane, infrastructure resources can be used as enforcement points for dynamic provisioning/configuring of security services according to the configurations received from upper layers.

B. Policy-based Federated Learning

To deploy the required entities for FL in the scenario described in the previous section, we devised an interoperable novel FL policy model containing all the necessary information. To this aim, we extended Medium-level Security Policy Language for Orchestration (MSPL-OP) since it provides multiple security capabilities, extending concepts from I2NSF IETF, is easily extensible and it has been used in relevant and related projects such as ANASTACIA or INSPIRE-5Gplus. Figure 2 shows the new proposed data model elements aimed to drive the FL policy intents. It will be used to deploy an FL agent or a FL aggregator. The colors used for the boxes in the diagram indicate whether a class is simple, i.e., it directly contains the value (lighter colors), or complex (darker colors), i.e., it contains other classes, either simple or complex.

As shown in the figure 2, there are two upper-level classes, *ITResourceOrchestration* and *ITResource* that indicate a resource will be deployed and configured in the infrastructure. In addition to an FL Agent and FL Aggregator, a resource could be another security entity such as the Anomaly Detection Engine or a monitoring probe. For the FL scenario, the *ITResource* is a *FederatedLearningRuleAction*, that will contain the necessary information to deploy either a FL Agent or a FL Aggregator. Inside this class, we can find blocks such as the *AggregatorParameters*, that contains the necessary information to deploy an aggregator (URL, FL rounds and fusion algorithm to be used), or an agent, that would need to know where the aggregator is located, but not the rounds or the fusion algorithm.

Moreover, there are blocks to indicate the Integration Fabric parameters (*IntegrationFabricParameters*), that in this example it is assumed to work as a publish/subscribe platform where information is stored and retrieved from topics, or to specify the details of the ML model to be trained, as part of the class

LearningModelInfo. In the case of a Deep Autoencoder for anomaly detection, we should set "unsupervised" in attribute *LearningType*, "neural network" in *Type* and "autoencoder" in *Subtype*. The *AdditionalParameters* attribute can be used to set more details about the model, such as the number of layers, the number of neurons in each layer or the loss function to be used.

Next, common learning parameters such as the test size, local epochs, steps per epoch and batch size can be set inside *LearningParameters*, and obfuscation mechanisms to elude membership inference attacks can be set inside *ObfuscationInfo*. For instance, setting "differential-privacy" in *Technique*, "Laplace Bounded Domain" in *Mechanism* and epsilon and delta values inside *AdditionalParameters*.

By last, the *InstanceThreshold* attribute represents the number of traffic samples, e.g., traffic flows, that has to be reached in order to register against the aggregator and start the federated training.

Fig. 2: Federated Learning policy model for Network Intelligence management

C. FL Orchestration process

The Federated Learning Orchestration process in a large-scale distributed B5G network is a crucial task that enables seamless coordination and collaboration among various entities involved, helping to configure, deploy and manage FL features. Figure 3 shows the proposed Federated Learning Orchestration process, involving several Security Management Domains at different levels (Core, Transport, RAN).

The orchestration process can be triggered in proactive or reactive ways depending on the source of the request. The proactive workflow starts with a user requesting FL features and capabilities to be deployed across the multi-domain infrastructure. The E2E Security Orchestrator analyzes

Fig. 3: FL Orchestration Process, proactive workflow

the requested capabilities and computes an orchestration plan to distribute the Federated Learning and anomaly detection tasks between underlying domains. To this aim, it generates as many FL security policies as needed, modeled in Medium-level Security Policy Language (MSPL) according to the FL-model defined in previous section, and commands them to the different domains (Fig. 3 steps 1 and 16). SMD orchestrators receive the MSPL-OP policy, composed of as many FL Agent policies as required and one FL Aggregator policy. Then, it retrieves the available security enablers, these are pieces of software or hardware able to implement the required capabilities, FL Agent and FL Aggregation (Fig. 3 step 2). When the Security Orchestrator has a list of enabler candidates, runs the allocation algorithm choosing the best suitable candidate and the best place to deploy the FL Agents and the FL Aggregator considering the context, environment and the constraints (Fig. 3 step 3). To perform the enforcement, the Security Orchestrator relies on the NFV-MANO component to deploy the agents and the aggregator in the required place (Fig. 3 step 4, 5 and 6). In the next step, the Security Orchestrator configures the enablers (FL Agents and FL Aggregator) with the parameters that have been requested (Fig. 3 step 7 and 8). The agents will register against the aggregator at the moment they reach the instance threshold. The aggregator, in collaboration with

these registered agents, will generate a new global model through the number of training rounds previously specified in the aggregator configuration policy (Fig. 3, step 9 and 10).

When the final model is ready, the FL Aggregator notifies the monitoring module (Fig. 3 step 11), which will trigger the Decision Engine (Fig. 3 step 12). The Decision Engine will generate a new MSPL policy, indicating FL Detection as the main capability, as well as the last model provided by the FL Aggregator (Fig. 3 step 13). The Security Orchestrator receives the request and performs again the orchestration process which in this case ends with the deployment of the AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine according to the trained model (Fig. 3 step 15).

D. FL-based Anomaly Detection

As shown in previous section, the proposal considers for the FL scenario, at least, one aggregator and multiple agents distributed across domains. Once deployed and configured, the traditional FL workflow takes place, in which agents train a separate model using their local traffic data as training data and the aggregator, through an iteration of learning rounds, mixes all particular models into a global one.

The model proposed for real-time anomaly detection tasks after training is a Deep Autoencoder. This type of model aims to reconstruct the input in the output. The idea is to

feed the Autoencoder with flow-based non-anomalous traffic samples extracted from the network as training data. Then, the autoencoder will become good at reconstructing these samples with a low error. Since the error can be measured dynamically, an error threshold can be defined for evaluating new traffic so that traffic flows exceeding the threshold will be classified as anomalies, as they significantly differ from the non-anomalous traffic dataset the model has been trained on.

The orchestrator will deploy and configure first the needed FL agents for model generation, and once a first model is obtained, AI-based Anomaly Detection Engines, provided with the model, will be deployed and will be able to discern between normal and anomalous samples. In case an anomaly is found, it will alert to upper lever components through the Integration Fabric so a further classification and final mitigation can be chosen and enforced over the infrastructure.

Once anomalies are detected, the framework is also able to perform reactive actions in real-time to apply proper countermeasures. This is, when an anomaly is detected by the AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine, it informs the Decision Engine which comes up with a set of mitigation policies to be orchestrated and enforced to mitigate the attack. As part of this reaction phase, the Decision Engine could command a new learning process so that the agents can offer the AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine a fresher model, updated with the latest status of the network, i.e., including the latest monitored data. Additional actions can also be taken, such as deploying more FL Agents and AI-based Anomaly Detection Engines across the infrastructure to protect some domains/subdomains that were not initially considered for the analysis.

It is important to highlight that the reactive stage of the framework is not fixed to improve FL features but providing a whole set of countermeasures. The decision module might infer different mitigation actions depending on the detected threat. For instance, it could generate a filtering policy to drop the malicious traffic as close as possible to the source, request the enforcing of a security slice to protect communications, deploying a honeynet, or assigning the attacker to a data-plane slice with the minimum QoS.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented an approach for orchestrating Network Intelligence in B5G networks driven by a Federated Learning architecture. The INSPIRE-5Gplus architecture has been leveraged to embrace the Federated Learning components aimed to realize ubiquitous AI. In addition, the paper proposes a proactive and reactive scalable and dynamic orchestration process aimed to manage and deploy, Federated Learning agents and AI-based Anomaly Detection engines that use the model generated previously to perform real-time detection. Moreover, an interoperable novel FL policy model, conceived to describe the behavior of the FL agent has been designed. The proposed Federated Learning architecture can be deployed automatically and efficiently in the B5G Continuum by means of a hierarchy of Network Intelligence orchestrators to handle anomaly and security threats in real-time.

This work will be continued with the implementation of the proposal, covering aspects such as performance metrics showing the advantages of using this approach to deploy FL-based anomaly detection mechanism in B5G networks.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. A. y. Arcas, "Communication-Efficient Learning of Deep Networks from Decentralized Data," in *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, ser. Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, A. Singh and J. Zhu, Eds., vol. 54. PMLR, 20–22 Apr 2017, pp. 1273–1282. [Online]. Available: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v54/mcmahan17a.html>
- [2] A. Khraisat, I. Gondal, P. Vamplew, and J. Kamruzzaman, "Survey of intrusion detection systems: techniques, datasets and challenges," *Cybersecurity*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 20, Jul 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42400-019-0038-7>
- [3] M. Injadat, A. Moubayed, A. Nassif, and A. Shami, "Multi-stage optimized machine learning framework for network intrusion detection," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. PP, pp. 1–1, 08 2020.
- [4] L. Fernández Maimó, L. Perales Gómez, F. J. García Clemente, M. Gil Pérez, and G. Martínez Pérez, "A self-adaptive deep learning-based system for anomaly detection in 5g networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 7700–7712, 2018.
- [5] E. M. Campos, P. F. Saura, A. González-Vidal, J. L. Hernández-Ramos, J. B. Bernabé, G. Baldini, and A. Skarmeta, "Evaluating federated learning for intrusion detection in internet of things: Review and challenges," *Computer Networks*, vol. 203, p. 108661, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128621005405>
- [6] J. Pei, K. Zhong, M. A. Jan, and J. Li, "Retracted: Personalized federated learning framework for network traffic anomaly detection," *Computer Networks*, vol. 209, p. 108906, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128622001001>
- [7] O. A. Wahab, A. Mourad, H. Otrok, and T. Taleb, "Federated machine learning: Survey, multi-level classification, desirable criteria and future directions in communication and networking systems," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 1342–1397, 2021.
- [8] T. Zhao, F. Li, and L. He, "Drl-based joint resource allocation and device orchestration for hierarchical federated learning in noma-enabled industrial iot," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 7468–7479, 2022.
- [9] M. Camelo, L. Cominardi, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Garcia-Saavedra, L. Fuentes, D. De Vleeschauwer, P. Soto-Arenas, N. Slammnik-Krijestorac, J. Ballesteros, C.-Y. Chang, G. Baldoni, J. M. Marquez-Barja, P. Hellinckx, and S. Latré, "Requirements and specifications for the orchestration of network intelligence in 6g," in *2022 IEEE 19th Annual Consumer Communications Networking Conference (CCNC)*, 2022, pp. 1–9.
- [10] S. D'Oro, L. Bonati, M. Polese, and T. Melodia, "Orchestrator: Network automation through orchestrated intelligence in the open ran," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2022 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*, 2022, pp. 270–279.
- [11] D. Bega, M. Gramaglia, R. Perez, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, and X. Costa-Pérez, "Ai-based autonomous control, management, and orchestration in 5g: From standards to algorithms," *IEEE Network*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 14–20, 2020.
- [12] P. Ruzafa-Alcázar, P. Fernández-Saura, E. Mármol-Campos, A. González-Vidal, J. L. Hernández-Ramos, J. Bernal-Bernabe, and A. F. Skarmeta, "Intrusion detection based on privacy-preserving federated learning for the industrial iot," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 1145–1154, 2021.